

CCG POLICY BRIEF

Economic Data Gaps & Challenges for Energy Systems Modelling: Coal Power

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Summary

Whilst coal has historically played an important role in electricity production, substantial concerns have been raised around its carbon emissions and subsequent contributions to climate change. Despite the rapid scale-up of renewables, the deployment of new coal-fired power stations persists in certain countries and regions, driven by cost considerations, rising energy consumption, and concerns over energy security. As nations grapple with the urgent need to phase out unabated coal power, understanding its associated costs and the measures needed to address asset stranding will be important to the development of energy and climate strategies.

These strategies heavily rely on technical insights from energy system models (ESMs), using tools such as OSeMOSYS. However, relevant insights on the cost of phasing out coal, including the extent of future asset stranding, are sensitive to assumptions around the cost of coal-fired power. In countries where there are challenges accessing empirical data, the development of policy recommendations using ESMs may be challenging. Here, we present global ranges taken from the open literature and discuss how they could be used to define and justify assumptions regarding the cost of unabated coal power.

Key Policy Recommendations

- Expansion of coal-fired power is incompatible with global climate goals and further deployment risks jeopardising climate goals and future stranding of coal assets.
- Academic researchers, government ministries, and other stakeholders operating in countries where there are challenges accessing empirical data can use costs drawn from global ranges.
- Global cost ranges from the open literature can be a useful tool to understand the extent of future asset stranding but are not a substitute for direct engagement with local developers and industry stakeholders.

Data Gaps & Challenges for Energy Systems Modelling of Coal Power

Introduction

Coal-fired power has played an important role in the global energy system historically, providing the fuel for the Industrial Revolution globally and supplying over a third of current global electricity production [1]. However, it is one of the most carbon-intensive sources of electricity and so its continued unabated use is incompatible with global and national climate targets. Despite this, global coal consumption reached an all-time high in 2022, and although demand is set to decline to 2026, there is substantial uncertainty over how quickly it will fall, particularly in Asia [2].

Despite its substantial contributions to greenhouse gas emissions, many nations and regions are continuing to construct new coal-fired power stations, a decision often driven by considerations around cost, energy security, and rising national energy consumption. To meet climate targets, there will need to be a rapid transition away from coal-fired power, with the International Energy Agency predicting in its Net Zero Emissions by 2050 Scenario that all unabated coal generation needs to end by 2040 at the latest if the world is to get to net zero by 2050 [1]. Despite this, 70 GW of new coal-fired power capacity was added to the global energy system in 2023 [3]

This policy brief outlines a curated dataset that presents global ranges of the technoeconomic parameters (eg capital cost, operating costs) which are key to modelling the costs of coal power, drawn from the open and grey literature. The aim of this brief is to discuss the challenges around data availability for coal power, especially in the Global South. In addition, the brief will provide energy system modellers and other stakeholders with a method of situating and justifying their cost assumptions to assess potential costs associated with asset stranding of unabated coal power in the absence of empirical data. This policy briefing also presents data on the costs of equipping coal with carbon capture, utilisation, and storage (CCUS), which would offer a route to reduce emissions whilst avoiding asset stranding due to climate commitments.

Drawing upon the existing literature base

Technoeconomic data on coal power were gathered to inform the assumptions used in large-scale energy systems modelling tools such as the OSeMOSYS [4]. Relevant data were collected from websites, reports, academic articles, and databases of national and international organisations. The data covers the range of parameters needed for the technoeconomic analysis of coal power, including operating and maintenance (O&M) costs, overnight capital costs, construction lead times and total operational lifetimes. The dataset has been made openly accessible in the Zenodo Data Repository and can be accessed via the following link: <https://zenodo.org/records/10890343>. The dataset shared on the Zenodo link contains the sources that were used to populate the database.

Global current capital costs for coal power

Error! Reference source not found. shows the range of overnight capital and fixed operating costs for the deployment of coal power, taken across 2020–2024. The capital costs extracted from the open literature between 2020–2024 show substantial variation, with a median value of 2,000, 5,046, and 6,910 USD/kW for non-lignite, lignite, and carbon capture, utilisation, and storage (CCUS) equipped coal-fired power stations. Data that were found in the open literature were predominantly from countries in Europe, Asia, and North America, with substantial data gaps for the rest of the world. There was a limited number of sources providing estimates on the costs of equipping coal-fired power with CCUS or building new CCUS equipped coal power, with capital costs over triple the costs of constructing a new non-lignite-based power station.

Figure 1: Range of a) capital costs and b) fixed operating costs for coal-fired power stations in 2020-2024, by category and stated in 2023 US dollar terms. The Unspecified category was for sources that reported costs for coal power, but did not indicate the type of coal power. The lower and upper bounds of each shaded box represent the lower and upper quartile of the data (25th and 75th percentile respectively), with the central line representing the median. Whiskers represent the range of values falling within 1.5 times the inter-quartile range, and outliers are shown with diamonds. The 25th, 50th, and 75th percentile values are written to the left of each bar.

Using global ranges to address empirical data gaps

Coal-fired power is expected to rapidly decline in the next few decades due to the scaling up of clean power from sources such as wind and solar PV, though it may continue to play a crucial role in iron and steel production until cleaner technologies become more cost-effective. The International Energy Agency predicts in its Net Zero Emissions by 2050 that the installed capacity of unabated coal power will fall from its current highs of 2,236 GW in 2022 to 242 GW by 2050, though installed capacity in countries such as China, India, and other Asian industrialising nations may continue to rise over the next decade [1].

Understanding the current costs of deployment for coal-fired power will be crucial to the design of retirement strategies and an effective phase-out of coal-fired globally. Error! Reference source not found. shows the range of capital costs between 2020–2024 by region (where available) and projected global costs in 2030 and 2050. As demonstrated by **Error! Reference source not found.**, many countries and regions across the globe have limited data availability on the costs of coal power in the open literature, which creates significant difficulties for policymakers, energy system modellers, and other stakeholders in understanding the extent of financial investments tied up in existing coal-fired power plants without direct engagement with operators.

Figure 2: Range of capital costs for coal-fired power stations in a) 2020–2024 for each world region, where available, and b) global projections for 2030 and 2050. Costs are stated in 2023 US dollar terms.

In countries and regions with limited data availability, it is important for policymakers, energy system modellers, and other stakeholders to clearly highlight the cost assumptions used in power and energy system modelling to support coal phase-out strategies. The extent of asset stranding and ability to retire coal-fired power in a cost-effective manner will be highly sensitive to the costs of coal power. Transparent documentation of assumptions and methodologies will also increase confidence in the modelling results, facilitating informed decision-making by policymakers and other stakeholders. The ranges presented in **Error! Reference source not found.** are intended to serve as a useful tool to situate assumptions in energy system models (ESMs) and other tools against empirical data taken from other countries and regions. This will help address the data gaps whilst still providing robust technical insights to support the development of coal-phase out strategies by policymakers.

Prioritising transparency and data sharing amongst stakeholders will also be essential to enhance the accuracy and utility of ESMs. By openly sharing data and methodologies, academic researchers, government ministries, industry professionals, and other stakeholders can work collaboratively to address data gaps, compare and contrast their assumptions, and so improve the reliability of energy system modelling outcomes. Given the potential sensitivity of ESMs to the costs of coal power, energy system modellers should also conduct sensitivity tests to assess the robustness of their models. Understanding how variations in cost assumptions impact model outcomes will be crucial for making informed decisions and developing resilient energy transition pathways, and situating their assumptions against the global cost curve could be a useful way of exploring model sensitivities.

However, whilst the global ranges from the open literature presented in this work can provide valuable insights and offer a way to address empirical data gaps, they should complement, not replace, direct engagement with private sector stakeholders. Collaborating with industry partners can enrich data collection efforts and ensure that ESMs accurately reflect real-world conditions and the true costs of coal power.

Conclusions

Addressing the challenges of data availability for coal power will be critical to accelerating the energy transition, particularly in countries in the Global South where there are risks of future asset stranding of coal-fired power. By recognising the importance of assumptions over the costs of coal power to coal phase-out strategies, and by justifying cost assumptions by using global ranges in regions with limited empirical data, stakeholders can enhance the accuracy and reliability of the scenarios generated from ESMs. However, whilst global ranges from the open literature can serve as useful reference points, engaging with private sector stakeholders will be essential for understanding and capturing the complexities of real-world deployment scenarios and charting effective coal phase-out strategies that avoid asset stranding.

References

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